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CONTENTS

HISTORICAL AND CULTURAL STUDIES ARTICLES

- Amina**
A Sulde Sang offering texts: Analysis of Genres and Text Modules 4
- Battuvshin Enkhtuvshin**
IL-Khan Hulegu through the Eyes of Vardan Arevelts'i 21
- Gabriel Arriel Pedrozo, Pietro de Castro Amaral, and Pedro Periera de Sequeira**
From Knight to Khan: A Comparative History of the Horse in Portuguese and Mongolian Culture in the Medieval Context 33
- Khatanbaatar Choidogsuren**
A Debate Between an Orphan Boy and Nine Great Meritorious Ministers of Chinggis Khan and 'Wisdom Precepts' of Chinggis Khan on Wine 43

ARCHAEOLOGICAL AND ANTHROPOLOGY

- Altansukh Ivanjav**
Mobile Settlement during the Mongol Empire
(on example of Tarvagtai Valley) 65
- Borbala Obrusánszky**
Hungarian Bean Sowing and Its Eastern Parallels 88
- Bumbayar Bavuudorj**
"Ovoo" and identity: Accumulation of spiritual and political power 97
- Sodbayar Ganbat**
Use of Chinggis Khan Prestige on Commercial in Post-Socialist Mongolia 106

ARTICLE

**FROM KNIGHT TO KHAN: A COMPARATIVE HISTORY OF THE HORSE
IN PORTUGUESE AND MONGOLIAN CULTURE IN THE MEDIEVAL
CONTEXT**

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Abstract: *Using Comparative History, this article explores social, cultural and symbolic aspects of Mongolian and Portuguese societies during the Middle Ages, through a common element: the horse. This research explores how this animal influenced the construction of military and social identities, standing out as a symbol of power and prestige. Despite different geographies and antagonistic contexts, the study of the ways in which this animal assumed distinct roles allows for an in-depth understanding of how this element was central to social and military organization. Thus, the study contributes to broadening the understanding of the diversity of uses and historical meanings attributed to the horse in different medieval societies.*

Keywords: Comparative history; horse symbolism; Mongolian society; Portuguese society; Middle Ages;

Introduction

Comparison is born when one knows the other. The exercise of historiography is always permeated by comparisons. Since the ancient Greeks such as Herodotus ¹ in Histories, Titus Livius ² in History of Rome or even Polybius ³ in Pragmatic History, the construction of the narrative of their texts does not discard the resource of comparison when detailing different peoples. In general, the historian in the exercise of writing and research, from time to time, always uses the comparison of societies in time, even if it is not through a

¹ Herodoto, 2019

² Livio, 2023

³ Políbio, 2016

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synthesized method. Not without reason, the famous French historian Paul Veyne states that all history is comparative history, something complemented by Cécile Vigour⁴ “the comparative method understood in a narrow sense is the foundation of the historian’s work, because he proceeds by crossing different sources”.

This is just one of many phrases from various works that deal with comparison. There are many examples and it is certainly not possible to exhaust them in the space of this introduction. In terms of method – or, perhaps it would be better to say, methodology –, Comparative History presents itself as a rich and complex historiographical field, the practice of which is capable of offering a unique opportunity to analyze distinctions and similarities between societies, whether they are in different times or spaces. As pointed out by historian Barros,⁵ there is a requirement in research in Comparative History for a reflective and rigorous stance, since “two or more objects studied in a comparative manner” require, in turn, a “specific way of doing history, of observing facts or analyzing sources”.⁶ Thus, through a multifocal analysis, where common aspects between different societies are subject to comparison, it is possible to illuminate specificities and human traits in antagonistic cultural universes. In this article, we seek, through comparative historiography, to investigate the role of the horse in Portuguese/Iberian and Mongolian societies, focusing on the medieval period, specifically at the end of the High Middle Ages and the beginning of the Late Middle Ages, according to the traditional Western division, a time marked by the emergence of emblematic characters and the consolidation of military and social strategies.

Comparative History, in its terms as a historiographical method, must always be aware of the various possibilities of anachronisms and false analogies, as warned by Bloch.⁷ Therefore, there is a need for rigor when establishing the bases for comparison and avoiding interpretations that distort specific historical contexts. In this article, when comparing two medieval societies: the Mongol and the Portuguese/Iberian, the influences of their respective geographic, economic and, above all, cultural contexts are considered in relation to a common and common element of these peoples: the horse. An animal that is configured as a central element for the movement and territorial control of both states that were just emerging at that time: on one side the vast Mongol Empire and on the other end of the Eurasian continent the first modern European state with a greater centralization of royal power, which was Portugal. Therefore, this article proposes to investigate the role of the horse in a comparative way in these different societies. Although it is tacitly known that the animal was crucial to both peoples, it assumed essentially distinct characteristics in each of them, reflecting their respective social, economic and cultural organizations. Through the comparative method, several documentary and historiographical sources were used to explore the relationship between man and horse in these two peoples. Since this relationship becomes a kind of interpretative key to understanding how the different cultures and their cosmologies visualize a transversally common element, as a point of convergence between them.

⁴ Vigour, 2005, p. 52

⁵ Barros, 2007

⁶ Barros, 2007, p. 1

⁷ Bloch, 1963

The Horse in Portuguese Society

The Christian kingdoms of the Iberian Peninsula, more specifically in the extremities of Western Europe, in the Medieval West, have a deep relationship with the horse, marked by a series of symbolisms. At the same time, the animal was recurrently present in the lives of common men. Before moving on to an example of a case of representation, such as in the song “um cavalo nom comeu” by João Garcia de Guilhade (approximately 1239~1270), we will discuss the usefulness of the horse in the Western Middle Ages.

One of the possible centers of domestication of the horse is in Kazakhstan,⁸ other hypotheses present stages of domestication of the animal and different lines, especially those carried out by the Scythian peoples in the Eurasian Plains⁹. There is no confirmed date for the beginning of the domesticated animal’s presence in Western Europe, however, the horse - even if wild - is the object of several cave paintings, such as in the Lascaux Cave, by ancient Europeans, 17 thousand years ago in France.

The European horse can be specified according to its use and its genetic “specialization”. We have: (1) the saggarius, which was the pack and draft horse, pulling carts and used for transportation. (2) the destrier, a combat horse, with horseshoes, bridle, high saddle, stirrups, etc., used by the rider. (3) The palfrey, a riding horse. (4) The mare used by ladies. (5) The mule or common horse. (6) Finally, the robust horse, used for carts and plows, replacing oxen, especially from the 12th and 13th centuries. Fundamentally devoted to war, the horse was very important to the knightly class, being present in several court romances and medieval epics. Thus, every destrier carries a name, such as Veillantif (Roland’s horse in the French epic: *La chanson de Roland*) or Ferrant (from Roussilon’s Girard). This noble war animal was often better treated than the servants of the nobility, while the farm horse, faster and more vigorous than oxen, although more expensive, was a better option for the farmer, making the animal an indispensable part of life in medieval Europe.

Let us therefore analyze a song written in Galician-Portuguese by João Garcia de Guilhade (1239~1270), in which a knight is satirized through the portrait of his horse that lives only on the providence of nature, in conditions of hunger and misery:

*A horse didn't eat
for six months, nor did he rise;
but it pleased God that it rained,
the grass grew,
and under it, he grazed,
and now he's good to go!
His owner didn't seek
barley for him, nor did he shoe him;
but the good weather returned,*

⁸ Outram, 2009

⁹ Librado, 2017

*the grass grew,
and he grazed, he bucked,
and now he's good to go!
His owner didn't want to give
barley to him, nor shoe him;
but, at the end of a swamp,
the grass grew,
and he grazed, he bucked,
and now he's good to go!*¹⁰

(Cantigas de escárnio e maldizer, João Garcia de Guilhade, séc. XIII)

In the poem, the horse is merged, through a symbolic analogy, with man himself, who is also subjected to the same sufferings as the animal, that is: fatigue “for six months, he has not even stood up”, hunger and the abandonment of his owner “His owner did not / look for barley for him, nor did he shoe him”. Thus, the God who provides for the horse’s sustenance, in reality, provides for the rider, or for the man who, similarly to the horse, finds himself in circumstances of poverty due to a bad owner; who here, allegorically, represents those men more endowed with power who on various occasions become responsible for the poorest. The poem, although it has a comic tone, typical of portuguese *cantiga*’s, still has a profound and very important message for its time: that God provides for the humble, the same message as the Sermon on the Mount: “Look at the birds of the air, for they neither sow nor reap nor gather into barns, and yet your heavenly Father feeds them. Are you not of much more value than they?”¹¹ It is important to note that this Christian vision was embedded in medieval European culture, as we can see in the songs, poems and other literary works of the time. This allegorical resource that brings the horse and rider together is common in Western initiation rites. The image of the horse, then, was widely explored in literature as a symbol representing the one who rides, that is, man himself.

In the West, the medieval initiation into knighthood has some similarities with horse symbolism, since the horse was privileged to bear the knight on his spiritual quest. In some respects its prototype is the battle between Bellerophon, mounted on pegasus, and the Chimera. Thus, having been regarded as seer and conductor of souls, the horse becomes the possessed, an initiate into divine mysteries, who abdicates his own personality so that that of a higher spirit can make itself manifest through it, a passive role indicated by the twofold meaning of ‘to mde’ and ‘to be ridden’. (Chevalier, Jean. 1969, p.204)

¹⁰ In medieval portuguese: “Um cavalo nom comeu/ há seis meses, nem s’ergeu;/ mais proug’a Deus que cho-veu,/ creceu a erva,/ e per cabo si paceu,/ e já se leva! / Seu dono nom lhi buscou/ cevada, nen’o ferrou;/ mailo bom tempo tornou, / creceu a erva, / e paceu, e arriçou, / e já se leva! / Seu dono nom lhi quis dar / cevada, nen’o ferrar; / mais, cabo d’um lamaçal, / creceu a erva, / e paceu, arriçou [ar], / e já se leva!” Cantigas de escárnio e maldizer, João Garcia de Guilhade, séc. XIII

¹¹ Matthew 6:24–33

We therefore find the image of the horse as the one that guides the soul; and, therefore, as flesh itself in relation to the soul, with the animal being the passive principle, guided by man, the active principle.

Corroborating this image of the horse as flesh, we also have the mythological image of the centaurs, a figure that is half man and half horse; which is recurrently described in myths as passionate beings, taken by lust, impulsiveness or anger, or even as powerful and strong beings.

The Horse in Mongolian Society The central role of the horse in nomadic civil and military life

The role of the horse in Mongolian nomadic life has been fully integrated into the lives of the inhabitants since time immemorial. In contrast to Europe, it is viewed not as a luxury but a necessity. From childhood, the Mongolian people are taught to familiarize themselves with horses. Many rural children help with various household chores and begin riding horses at the age of 4 or 5.¹² Due to the importance of the horse and its dependence on the climate and vegetation, the life of pastoral nomads also becomes dependent on the climate. Therefore, “when the climate is favorable the herders are rich”.¹³ When analyzing this aspect of Mongolian life and its dependence on climatic factors, it is deducible that they would not do very well in distant military campaigns, but the Mongols proved to be experienced and resilient warriors. As in civilian life, much of the organization and military life revolved around the horse. Mongolian horses were very resilient. They did not need constant provisions because they got their food from the open field, like wild horses, and they drank little water, often needing to drink water only once a day even in hot weather.¹⁴ The Mongols had the habit of milking mares and using it to make “airag,” a fermented mare’s milk drink.¹⁵ They also drank the blood of horses when water was scarce.

In the time of Genghis Kahn, war horses were well cared for. The Mongols were some of the best horsemen in the world and were capable of performing incredible acrobatics on their horses, their grace and skill being compared even to ballet dancers.¹⁶ In a letter to his general Subutai, Genghis Kahn instructs his general on how his soldiers should treat their horses on a daily basis and that they should tighten the horse’s bridle when hunting, ordering that any man who disobeys should have his head cut off.¹⁷ This punishment demonstrates that the horse for the Mongols was not just property but a companion and a valuable asset that should be respected and well treated. Furthermore, it is observed that, in Mongolian poetry, horses generally symbolize leadership. This animal can assume several representations, such as companionship, loyalty and leadership. As a metaphor, the horse can mean guidance and strength, attributes of a leader.

Due to these factors, it is safe to say that the relationship of Mongol warriors with their horses went beyond just the practicality of everyday life and the use of this animal as a

¹² Brunn, 1953, p. 104

¹³ Brunn, 1953, p 51

¹⁴ Haslund, 1934, p. 110

¹⁵ Yazdzik, 2011, p. 24

¹⁶ Haslund, 1934, p. 111

¹⁷ Onon, 2001, p. 183 and 184

tool of war. For these people, horses were an inseparable part of life. They were a source of food,¹⁸ daily work,¹⁹ companions at home and also during military campaigns.

The importance of the horse in Mongolian mythology and religion

It is not known exactly how the religious practices of the Mongols worked before their empire. They were a people who knew spirituality and had habits and practices that we can consider “religious” but the details of these practices have unfortunately been lost.²⁰ It is often said today that the Mongols practiced a kind of “shamanism”. This may be wrong, because once the Mongols acquired a word for the concept of religion (nom in the mid-14th century), they used this word to recognize some modern religions such as Buddhism, Christianity, Taoism and Islam, but not for others such as Confucianism.²¹ Of course, there is still debate today about whether Confucianism is in fact a religion, but the Mongols also did not consider their own religious experts (shamans) to be part of a religion, nor did they consider them astrologers, fortune-tellers, or Chinese yin-yang masters.²² That said, it is clear that the Mongols did have a spiritual and (depending on the definition used) religious system. As evidence of the importance of horses in this system, we have the fact that many Mongol warriors were buried with their horses. At Genghis Khan’s funeral, at least forty horses were buried next to the emperor.²³ Thus, we do not know exactly how important the horse was in the Mongol “religion” at the time of Genghis Khan, but we do know that some kind of ritualistic importance existed.

Comparison and Analysis

In both societies, the horse is fundamentally devoted to war. Not without reason, it has been the subject of several theories to explain the mobility and migration of peoples in the distant past, such as the spread and arrival of Indo-European speakers in Europe²⁴. This animal has a very ancient context of warlike use.²⁵ In the far west, its use in combat began to gain more prominence with the arrival of Germanic peoples from the steppes at the end of the fall of the Roman Empire, constituting a shared element of several medieval European armies. Interestingly, it is in war that its use is found, which is common between the Mongol and Portuguese cases, although with its own striking particularities.

In medieval Portuguese society, in many cases, the horse was an element of prestige and social distinction, especially among the warrior nobility. The use of this animal was strongly associated with hierarchy and power. In the far west of Europe, the use of this animal in combat has always tended to be more limited. The geographical conditions in the small Portuguese kingdom would not allow for long maneuvers with large masses of cavalry, whereas on the plains such tactics would be more widely used (as in Mongolia). This more limited use of such a powerful animal gives prominence to the one who possesses it.

¹⁸ Yazdzik, 2011, p. 24

¹⁹ Brunn, 1953, p. 104

²⁰ Elverskog, 2023, p 529

²¹ Elverskog, 2023, p 529

²² Elverskog, 2023, p. 529

²³ Rossabi, 1994, p. 3

²⁴ Damgaard, 2018

²⁵ Librado, 2017

Figura 1: At the top, the use of horses in combat (Mongols on the left and Portuguese on the right). At the bottom, the common use of the animal, (Mongols in hunting on the left and Portuguese in riding and patrolling on the right). Source: Image collage. (DER BUNDESREPUBLIK DEUTSCHLAND, 2005, p. 256; EBREY et al., 1996, p. 179; CSM Códice Rico, f. 147 e 172). Access in <https://renopen-rose.getarchive.net/media/portuguese-and-english-armies-defeating-a-french-vanguard-of-the-king-of-castile-7a0a90>, november by 2024.

In contrast the medieval Portuguese knight was a singular unit, the Mongolian knight was a plural unit. The most famous example of this use was precisely that carried out by Genghis Khan, who employed a military force focused on rapid and decisive movement, where the resistance and agility of the Mongolian knights were used for surprise tactical maneuvers.²⁶ The Mongolian knights – unlike Western Europeans – often combined riding and composite bows, allowing them to fire continuously, a great advantage against slower infantry units, such as the Chinese at the time.²⁷ In addition to these tactics, the one that differs most from the common use of Europeans was the recurrence in some cases of Mongolian knights organized in dispersed formations, which allowed coordinated attacks and rapid retreats, carrying out ambushes.²⁸

However, in the symbolic and cultural field, there are also some connections. The respect and social representation of a mounted warrior (whether Portuguese or Mongolian) was significant in their society. In Mongolian society, the horse was a symbol of status and survival, representing both military and economic value. Unlike Europeans, these warriors owned herds of horses, which reinforced their social position within nomadic communities.²⁹ These horsemen represented positions of importance in their families and clans. Their loyalty to these two institutions was valued, and these men contributed to the protection and subsistence of their family groups.³⁰

In the Portuguese case, the horse had a more restrained and limited use. The combat horse was not part of the daily life of the Portuguese knight or the common man in such an integrated way as in the Mongolian case. Because it was an extremely agrarian society

²⁶ Ramirez, 2000

²⁷ Ostrowski, 2010

²⁸ Morgan, 1979

²⁹ Waddington, 1974

³⁰ Shallal and Darweesh, 2023

with fixed settlements, in Western Europe there were several breeds of animals that were used for cargo, to pull carts, or as riding horses for the nobility and more robust animals for carts and plows – although their use was more widespread in the 12th and 13th centuries, replacing oxen.³¹

Despite its more utilitarian roles, even with ordinary uses, the combat horse remains the noblest of all domestic animals. Cared for by several servants, and allocated in times of war alongside its master, it is an animal symbolically celebrated in several medieval poems, earning names and biographies in the literature of its time.³² As can be seen above in the text, the horse is confused, through a resource of symbolic analogy, with man himself. A creature also subjected to the same sufferings as its master. For the knight of the Iberian Peninsula, the horse was a representative symbol of the one who rides, that is, man himself, and a passive principle, guided by man, the active principle.

In short, the comparison between the use and representation of the horse in both contexts highlights the way in which social relations and cultural demands are established around a common element. While for the Mongols the horse was an animal with strong ties and of vital importance in the sphere of the lives of thousands of people, in Portugal, it assumed a role of distinction and represented an ideal of knighthood strongly aligned with Christianity and the feudal ethos. The differentiating perspective, according to Tilly,³³ allows us to observe how the same element – in this case, the horse – can acquire specific functions and meanings according to the structures and values of each society.

Therefore, this analysis undertaken here allows us to see the fundamental differences between the two societies. As Barros³⁴ argues, the comparative method helps to “reveal the structures” underlying the uses and meanings attributed to an element, such as the horse, in different contexts. It promotes an in-depth analysis of social relations and practices in the medieval period. Despite cultural differences, the horse was a strategic and central resource in both societies, standing out as a social, cultural and religious symbol.

Conclusion

In both societies, the horse played a multifaceted and crucial role in social, military and economic development. In the Iberian context, the horse was a symbol of power and prestige, linked to the hierarchical structure of the nobility and the military organization of the cavalry. Portuguese society, still in the process of forming its identity, saw the horse as a means of expressing strength and honor, deeply influencing its war culture and contributing to the consolidation of a military ethos. On the other hand, for the Mongols, under the command of figures such as Genghis Khan, the horse was the basis of a military system entirely dependent on equestrian skills. The mobility conferred by the horse, combined with Mongol martial skill, shaped a society in which adaptability and expansion were central elements.

³¹ Le Goff, 2002

³² Le Goff, 2002

³³ Tilly, 1984

³⁴ Barros, 2007

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